

The Mint Versus Covid Hypothesis: Practicalities

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There is a growing body of scientific literature suggesting that eating mint family herbs might prevent or treat Covid ([Buck, 2022b](#)). The purpose of this supplemental file is to report my individual efforts to develop simple and enjoyable culinary approaches that might eventually help promote volunteer compliance in future randomized controlled trials testing the mint versus Covid hypothesis. I explored a wide range of fresh and dried herb combinations, both out of epicurean interest and based on a desire to implement the general nutritional theory that it's healthy to eat a varied diet.

Throughout the pandemic, I have carefully followed public health guidance on vaccination, testing, distancing, and masking. The hypothesis at hand is simply that mint might serve as an additional complementary measure that could further help me fend off Covid. Clinical trials of Paxlovid (and reasoning from general principles) suggest that entirely preventing SARS-CoV-2 infection may be more difficult than blunting the infection after a person has tested positive. At the same time, experience with SARS-CoV-2-neutralizing monoclonal antibodies supports the concept that antiviral medicines are generally more effective for blunting an infection if taken early. In other words, even if a therapeutic doesn't fully prevent infection there might still be benefit in having the therapeutic onboard prior to testing positive for Covid. With these thoughts in mind, I explored ways to expand my routine day-to-day consumption of mint family herbs.

Loose-leaf single-herb domestic tea products were preferred, when available, because appearance and flavor can be used to guard against counterfeiting and adulteration ([Das et al., 2022](#); [Piller, 2022](#); [Schwalfenberg et al., 2013](#)). I also reoriented a longstanding back-deck container-gardening hobby to focus on mint family herbs (see Table 1, below).

Recipe 1: Hot tea. A key early advance in the discovery of the antimalarial drug artemisinin was the realization that the active compounds in wormwood leaves are degraded by boiling water ([Tu, 2011](#)). Although Le-Trilling and colleagues showed that antiviral compounds in mint family herbs persist in boiling water ([Le-Trilling et al., 2022](#)), it remains conceivable that some fraction of the hypothetical anti-SARS-CoV-2 compounds in mint family herbs might be destroyed by high temperature. On the other hand, there could theoretically be heat-stable antiviral compounds that are extracted more efficiently in boiling water. To address this dilemma, I perform a double extraction. Ten to 15 grams (3-4 heaping tablespoons) of loose-leaf mint family tea products are placed in a French press (Frieling) and stirred together with a few hundred milliliters (1½

cups) of room temperature water for a few minutes. I then press the leaves and drink the cool water extract. The drained leaves are then re-extracted with several hundred milliliters of near-boiling water for >10 minutes and consumed as a hot tea. An infuser basket (OXO) also offers a convenient way to perform double-extractions.

Teas employ a rotating variety of fresh or dried herbs listed in Table 1. Staple products include bohe mint (Ouyang Hengzhi or Plum Flower), peppermint (Harts of America), spearmint (Harts of America) and thyme (Anthony's). Although perilla (Prince Herb) makes a somewhat strange-tasting single-herb tea, it contributes useful background complexity to mixed-herb teas.

I enjoy small amounts of fresh oregano, rosemary, and sage in savory dishes, but I find teas made from the dried herbs unappealing. I'm also cognizant of the risk of consuming too much thujone, which is abundant in sage ([Lachenmeier & Uebelacker, 2010](#)). Like oregano, self-heal flower spikes were shown to have high antiviral potency in Jan and colleagues' cell culture-based infectivity model ([Jan et al., 2021](#)). In contrast to oregano, self-heal (Plum Flower) makes a mild-flavored tea that blends well with other herbs.

For many years, I have enjoyed a roughly five cup per day coffee habit. During the Omicron waves, I adopted the new habit of substituting two or three daily cups of coffee with one or two batches of mixed-herb tea. For the substitute cups, I sometimes supplement the mint family herb mixture with yerba mate (Cruz de Malta), with the goal of adding both caffeine and the proposed anti-Covid compound caffeic acid ([Le-Trilling et al., 2022](#)) (Table 1). Yaupon, which is closely related to yerba mate, is also a good complement for the flavors of herb teas. Harts of America Super Antioxidant Green Tea (yaupon, spearmint) and Lost Pines Light Roast Yaupon are current favorites.

When I learn that a friend or family member has tested positive for SARS-CoV-2, I first recommend that they attempt to obtain Paxlovid ([Buck, 2022a](#)) and then I send them a gift of mint tea. Celestial Seasonings Mint Magic (spearmint, peppermint, chickory, cinnamon, and orange peel) and Pukka Three Mint (peppermint, spearmint, field mint) ship quickly and make enjoyable teas. On the gift label, I advise the Covid-positive loved one to consider drinking two mugs of mint tea a day, making each mug with four tea bags. I express the hope that they will enjoy mint tea as a possible complement to proven Paxlovid therapy.

Recipe 2: Iced Tea. Drinking a daily glass of strong iced tea is a convenient way to achieve the 200 mg/kg/day dose that Jan and colleagues showed to be effective for treating SARS-CoV-2 infection in hamsters ([Jan et al., 2021](#)). Approximately 50 grams

(1⅔ cups) of loose-leaf mint family herb tea products are mixed with roughly half a liter (one pint) of room-temperature water for about an hour. The cool-water extract is poured into a pitcher using a funnel fitted with a mesh strainer and the retained leaves are re-steeped in half a liter of near-boiling water for about an hour. The cooled hot-water extract is then strained and combined with the initial cool-water extract. An optional 25 grams of honey (1 tablespoon) or 40 grams (scant ¼ cup) of table sugar per liter of iced tea balances herbal bitterness without being overly sweet. Excellent iced teas can be produced with the same herb combinations used for hot tea.

Recipe 3: Fresh Herbs. For many years, I have been in the routine habit of enhancing daily salads with a small handful (5-10 grams) of fresh herbs. Mint family herbs that are easy to grow and have enjoyable flavor profiles include – roughly in descending order of my personal preference for eating by the handful – basil, spearmint, peppermint, Vietnamese balm, perilla, sacred basil, lemon balm, Moldavian dragonhead, tulsi basil, self-heal, hyssop, oregano, rosemary, sage, and American skullcap (Table 1).

At times when I suspect my household might have been exposed to SARS-CoV-2, I serve mixed-herb pesto over pasta or beans ([Luchtel, 2022](#)). Traditional pesto recipes call for breaking open plant cell walls using a mortar and pestle. Some modern recipes instead call for pre-softening plant cell walls by briefly blanching the herbs in boiling water prior to chopping in a food processor ([Colicchio, 2001](#)). To avoid the possibility of losing hypothetical antiviral compounds to the blanching water ([Jyotshna et al., 2018](#)) I instead freeze the herbs ([López-Alt, 2015](#)) just prior to chopping in a food processor.

Recipe 4: Other Foods. Although fresh self-heal leaves aren't particularly flavorful, they have excellent tender texture reminiscent of Bibb lettuce. Self-heal leaves are useful for sandwiches.

Perilla (also known as shiso) is sometimes used in ice creams, sorbets, and cocktails. A simple syrup made with red perilla (Prince Herb) develops an attractive red-plum color when acidified with lemon juice. The flavor of perilla cocktail syrup marries well with the herbal profiles of Lamiaceae-infused liquors such as vermouth, absinthe, and amaro.

All sampled brands of za'atar, which contains the mint family herb *Zataria multiflora*, are palatable sprinkled on bread, salad, or yogurt. Although nigella (*Nigella sativa*) is not a member of the mint family, its seeds have been reported to have possible anti-Covid effects in an RCT ([Ashraf et al., 2021](#); [Ashraf et al., 2022](#)). Nigella seeds are suitable for all culinary applications where one might use sesame seeds.

Dried black chokeberries (Powbab) are a pleasant food either eaten whole or as an adjunct to mixed-herb teas. Sunflower seeds are a convenient snack food and make a pleasant substitute for pine nuts in pesto.

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Common name	Species	Inhibitory dilution	Caffeic acid	Growth	Taste	Citations
Anise hyssop	<i>Agastache foeniculum</i>	nt	80	++	++	[1, 2]
Korean hyssop	<i>Agastache rugosa</i>	nt	1600	+++	++	[3]
Black chokeberry	<i>Aronia melanocarpa</i> *	nt (>30)	1500	nt	+	[4-6]
Sweet wormwood	<i>Artemisia annua</i> *	≥128 (~125)	150	++	++	[7-10]
Cinnamon (twig)	<i>Cinnamomum cassia</i> *	320	400	nt	++	[11]
Cuban oregano	<i>Coleus amboinicus</i>	64	640	+	++	[12]
Dragonhead	<i>Dracocephalum moldavica</i>	nt	75	++	++	[13]
Vietnamese balm	<i>Elsholtzia ciliata</i>	nt	50	+++	++	[14]
Sunflower (seed)	<i>Helianthus annuus</i> *	nt	80	nt	++	[5, 15]
Fish mint	<i>Houttuynia cordata</i> *	320	10	++	+	[16]
Hyssop	<i>Hyssopus officinalis</i>	nt	80	++	++	[2, 17]
Yerba mate	<i>Ilex paraguariensis</i> *	nt	1500	nt	+	[18, 19]
Yaupon	<i>Ilex vomitoria</i> *	nt	1500	nt	++	[20]
Lavender (flower)	<i>Lavandula angustifolia</i>	nt	150	++	+	[21, 22]
Lemon balm	<i>Melissa officinalis</i>	nt	300	++	++	[2, 23, 24]
Wild mint	<i>Mentha canadensis</i>	nt	<50	++	+	[25]
Bohe mint	<i>Mentha haplocalyx</i>	480	600	+	++	[26]
Spearmint	<i>Mentha spicata</i>	nt	200	++	++	[2, 5, 24, 27]
Peppermint	<i>Mentha x piperita</i>	nt	800	++	++	[28, 29]
Wild bergamot	<i>Monarda fistulosa</i>	nt	600	-	nt	[2]
Horsemint	<i>Monarda punctata</i>	nt	150	-	++	[2]
Japanese catnip	<i>Nepeta tenuifolia</i>	640	nt	nt	nt	
Catmint	<i>Nepeta x faassenii</i>	nt	250	++	+	[2]
Nigella seeds	<i>Nigella sativa</i> *	nt	3000	-	+	[30-32]
African blue basil	<i>O. kilimandscharicum x basilicum</i>	nt	nt	+++	++	
Lemon basil	<i>Ocimum x africanum</i>	nt	~100	+	++	[33]
Basil	<i>Ocimum basilicum</i>	64	~100	++	++	[22, 33]
Tulsi basil	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i>	nt	<10	++	++	[34]
Sacred basil	<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i>	nt	~150	+++	++	[33]
Dittany	<i>Origanum dictamnus</i>	nt	600	+	+	[35]
Oregano	<i>Origanum vulgare</i>	960	2000	++	+	[5, 36]
Perilla (seed)	<i>Perilla frutescens</i>	<4	20	nt	nt	[37]
Perilla	<i>Perilla frutescens</i>	640 (~100)	300	+++	+	[38-40]
Patchouli	<i>Pogostemon cablin</i>	64	nt	nt	-	
Self-heal (flower)	<i>Prunella vulgaris</i>	960	1800	++	++	[24]
Mountain mint	<i>Pycnanthemum virginianum</i>	nt	nt	+	++	
Pineapple sage	<i>Salvia elegans</i>	nt	1500	++	+	[41]
Greek sage	<i>Salvia fruticosa</i>	nt	1700	nt	+	[42]
Chia (seed)	<i>Salvia hispanica</i>	≥128	60	nt	-	[43]
Red sage (root)	<i>Salvia miltiorrhiza</i>	<4	nt	nt	nt	
Sage	<i>Salvia officinalis</i>	nt (~100)	500	++	+	[5, 22, 24, 27, 38, 41]
Rosemary	<i>Salvia rosmarinus</i>	≥128	100	++	++	[5, 22, 24, 27]
Baical skullcap (root)	<i>Scutellaria baicalensis</i>	32	nt	+	+	
Barbat skullcap	<i>Scutellaria barbata</i>	≥128	nt	+	+	[2]
American skullcap	<i>Scutellaria lateriflora</i>	nt	nt	++	+	
Conehead thyme	<i>Thymus capitatus</i>	nt	800	-	nt	[44]
Thyme	<i>Thymus vulgaris</i>	nt (~100)	300	+	++	[5, 24, 27, 38]
Coltsfoot (flower)	<i>Tussilago farfara</i> *	480	2000	nt	nt	[45]
Za'atar thyme	<i>Zataria multiflora</i>	nt	nt	+	++	

Table 1: Key characteristics of botanical products of interest. Entries refer to the leaves of the plant, unless otherwise indicated. Non-Lamiaceae species are marked with asterisks. The “Inhibitory dilution” column indicates the most dilute SARS-CoV-2-inhibitory dose (in fold dilution starting from a 25 mg/ml extract) reported Jan and colleagues' cell culture testing [46]. The abbreviation "nt" indicates not tested. In some instances, the rough equivalent inhibitory dilution observed in other studies is given in parentheses. The “Caffeic acid” column lists the rough average concentration of unconjugated caffeic acid (in micrograms per gram of dry plant material) reported in the cited references. The caffeic acid value should not be considered a comprehensive average of all available publications, but merely an aggregate based on references that seemed most salient in Google Scholar searches. The “Growth” column lists the vigor of plant growth in a pesticide-free drip-irrigated back-deck amateur container garden in Bethesda, Maryland, USA. The “Taste” column indicates the author's individual opinion about the overall culinary appeal of each plant product.

Table 1 References

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